

Adaptive Interoperable Management of Hybrid Energy Storage Systems for Grid-Forming Services

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Abstract—This paper proposes an adaptive and interoperable management framework for Hybrid Energy Storage Systems (HESS) integrated with grid-forming converters to address the challenges of low-inertia power grids. The framework coordinates ultracapacitors and batteries through a hierarchical control structure to jointly deliver critical grid-forming services, including virtual inertia emulation and voltage dip mitigation for improved transient stability. A central innovation is the Intelligent Node Management System (InMS), which incorporates the State of Function (SoF) as a unifying language for real-time monitoring, hybridization, and allocation of storage resources within a standards-compliant interoperable architecture. The SoF-based adaptive approach dynamically tunes the inertial parameters of the grid-forming converter according to grid events, thereby enhancing system resilience during disturbances. Interoperability is further supported by a Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC), enabling seamless integration of different devices. The effectiveness of the proposed framework, covering seamless islanding, smooth resynchronization, and reinforcement of weak grids, has been demonstrated in a pilot project in Spain, combining PSCAD simulations with megawatt-scale laboratory testing. The results confirm the practical viability of the approach and highlight the importance of hybridization with adaptive interoperable operation of HESS in low-inertia systems.

Index Terms—Hybrid energy storage, Interoperability, Grid forming converter, Low inertia systems, Adaptive control.

I. INTRODUCTION

The global energy transition has accelerated the integration of renewable energy sources such as wind and solar into power systems. These inverter-based resources (IBRs), typically interfaced via power electronic converters, are rapidly displacing traditional synchronous generators, contributing to reduction in system inertia [1], [2]. Unlike conventional generators, inverter-based plants using Grid-Following (GFL) converters do not inherently support system stability in terms of inertial response or grid-forming capabilities, thereby introducing significant operational and dynamic stability concerns in low-inertia grids [3], [4].

To address these challenges, Grid-Forming (GFM) converters have been developed to emulate the dynamic

behavior of synchronous generators. Unlike GFL inverters, GFM units can establish and regulate voltage and frequency independently of the grid, thus enabling critical services such as inertia emulation, autonomous voltage support, and islanded operation. In this context, a new generation of control strategies, including Virtual Synchronous Machines (VSMs) and self-synchronization loops [5]–[9], has emerged to facilitate the adoption of GFM systems in real-world applications. However, providing these advanced services requires a fast and flexible source of energy at the DC side of the converter, something that single-technology Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) often struggle to provide efficiently due to degradation and sizing limitations.

Transmission System Operators (TSOs) are increasingly recognizing that many challenges in low-inertia distributed generation environments are inherently related to power-based requirements, necessitating fast-response capabilities to deliver services such as frequency regulation, fast peak shaving, virtual inertia emulation, and power smoothing. These services are particularly critical in low-inertia power systems with high shares of renewable generation, where conventional storage solutions are not sufficient. A common challenge has been the oversizing of battery-only energy storage systems (BESS) typically based on lithium-ion technology to meet short-term high-power demands. However, this approach leads to significant increases in both capital and operational expenditure (CAPEX and OPEX), undermining the economic viability of the system. Moreover, relying on single storage technology for power-intensive services results in non-optimal sizing and accelerated degradation, particularly when the technology is not well-suited for high-frequency cycling requirements [2].

To overcome this limitation, the focus is given to Hybrid Energy Storage Systems (HESS) that combine ultracapacitors (UCAPs) with lithium-ion batteries. This architecture enables the decoupling of power and energy delivery, allowing UCAPs to respond rapidly to transient grid events while batteries handle longer-duration energy needs. By optimizing the energy and power layers separately, HESS can deliver enhanced dynamic services such as virtual inertia, frequency regulation and power oscillation damping (POD) while improving system lifetime and reducing operational costs [10]. Despite the technical feasibility of HESS-enabled GFM control, industrial deployment requires more than just converter-level enhancements [11]–[14]. Interoperability evolves into complex networks of distributed and heterogeneous assets; interoperability has become a critical requirement for seamless integration and coordinated

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operation [15]-[17]. In this regard, the proposed approach of [16] have been extensively extended the HESS-GFM system with a complementary control layer, incorporating an interoperable energy management tool consisting of state of the function (SoF) and hybridization algorithms within the use of Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC), as developed within the framework of recent European research projects such as Inertia+ [17] and InterSTORE [18]. The InMS enables hierarchical multi-service orchestration across different storage and converter systems, while the LPC bridges communication between legacy field devices (e.g., Modbus) and modern energy management systems through standardized protocols such as IEEE 2030.5 and NATS middleware [19].

The main focus of this paper is the development and demonstration of advanced control architecture for hybrid energy storage systems designed to enhance the performance of GFM converters in low-inertia power networks. By coordinating ultracapacitors and lithium-ion batteries, the system combines the fast dynamics of high-power storage with the energy capacity of batteries, overcoming the limitations of battery-only configurations. This hybridization improves response to services such as virtual inertia, frequency regulation, and power oscillation damping, while reducing battery stress and extending system lifetime.

Building on our earlier work [16], this paper introduces significant advancements through the integration of a hierarchical and interoperable management system. The proposed Intelligent Node Management System (InMS) incorporates adaptive inertia tuning and real-time coordination using standardized communication protocols (e.g., IEEE 2030.5, NATS). This interoperability layer bridges legacy field devices and modern EMS platforms, enabling secure and scalable management across multi-vendor systems. The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- State of Function (SoF) based algorithms as a unifying language for managing heterogeneous storage assets, fully embedded within a hierarchical management framework spanning device, coordination, and EMS levels.
- Novel SoF-based integration of adaptive inertia and damping within a hybrid EMS framework which unlike existing adaptive VSM methods, the proposed scheme embeds inertia tuning directly into an interoperable InMS, coordinating ultracapacitors and batteries via SoF indices.
- SoF-based hybridization, enabling dynamic allocation of fast-response and energy-dominant services between UCAP and BESS in real time.
- Interoperability layer using LPC and SoF virtualization, which ensures seamless multi-vendor integration and standards-based communication (IEEE 2030.5, NATS), extending beyond converter-level approaches.

Beyond the methodological developments, the paper also provides practical implementation insights from an ongoing pilot project in Spain, which is the first of its kind to combine grid-forming control and UCAP-BESS hybridization with SoF-based adaptive management. These contributions collectively advance both the theoretical and applied aspects of hybrid storage integration in low-inertia power systems.

II. HIERARCHICAL CONTROL STRUCTURE

The general hierarchical control structure for performing the different control levels for a GFM conversion-based generation unit is presented in Fig. 1. For flexible and high-level controls, an InMS as an advanced energy management tool is designed and used for validating the HESS GFM system capabilities. Modbus over TCP is used for its communication. As shown in Fig. 1, the first control level (CTRL1) consists of the inner current controller, power electronic level, which can provide the modulated signals.

Fig. 1. General control structure of the GFM power converter-based unit for dynamic studies.

The second control level (CTRL2) is mainly related to the outer loop controllers and grid functionalities, which gives proper input signal to CTRL1. Additional grid functionalities can be utilized as part of CTRL2 to CTRL4 outer loop controls such as Energy management tools, Virtual inertia and Frequency control or POD services. The core of the grid forming action is presented in Fig. 2 which is located at the CTRL2 level for managing the voltage and angle. In this framework, the DC side is shared between battery and UCAP in a way that fast response actions can be covered by UCAP and the rest by Battery. By mixing these two technologies, in the scheme of a hybrid solution, different types of services like fast peak shaving, simultaneous virtual inertia, frequency control and POD can be provided. Fig. 2 shows the supplementary control loops used as the VSM control (synchronous generator emulation) with electromechanical characteristics and reactive power/voltage droop control.

Fig. 2. Outer control loop at the CTRL2 level.

The transfer function of a generic power loop control which represents the mechanical part of a generator is written as:

$$T_{PLC}(s) = \frac{\omega_n^2/K_s}{s + 2\zeta\omega_n} \quad (1)$$

where ζ is damping factor, ω_n is the natural frequency and K_s is the synchronization coefficient which represent the maximum active power that can be delivered according to the external plant characteristics:

$$K_s = \frac{E V}{X} \quad (2)$$

where E , V and X are internal *emf* voltage, grid voltage and overall plant impedance, respectively. Usually, the values for E and V are close to the rated ones and the value for the load angle (δ), uses to be very small. Under such conditions, the value of $\sin(\delta)$ can be simply approximated by δ , and the delivered electrical power can be approximated to ($P_{out} = \frac{E V}{X} \delta$). Transmitted power can be regulated by shifting the converter's output voltage phase. The relationship between the input and output power of such a grid-forming system can be led to the following representation:

$$\frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} = \frac{\omega_n^2}{s^2 + 2\zeta\omega_n s + \omega_n^2} = \frac{\frac{K_s}{2H}}{s^2 + \frac{D}{2H}s + \frac{K_s}{2H}} \quad (3)$$

where P_{in} , P_{out} , H and D are per unit input power, delivered active power, the inertia constant in sec and damping constant respectively. The self-synchronization mechanism, shown in Fig. 2, allows the converter to operate in synchronism with an external grid. There are different variants of self-synchronization mechanisms, such as power-frequency droop control (P-f) or virtual synchronous machine control [4]. This mechanism results in reference angle output, which will be an input to CTRL2. Following the functionalities of CTRL 1 and 2 for grid-forming control and inertia emulation, the next levels are CTRL3 and 4 devoted to higher-level management layer. This supervisory layer is responsible for coordinating multiple assets through an advanced InMS, which incorporates novel features such as adaptive and interoperable control for hybrid energy systems. In this hierarchy, CTRL3 (Coordination level) is responsible for coordinating different storage units, handling functions such as power sharing, service prioritization, and load balancing. CTRL4 (Virtualization /EMS level) will implement high-level interoperability through the InMS and SoF framework, enabling high-level coordination with multiple storage units and services, with parameter adaptation, exposing services to external SCADA/TSO via LPC protocols.

One important aspect of higher level coordinated control at CTRL3 is the droop-based control which can be coordinated with inertial response managed by InMS tool. In such application, the converter's active and reactive power setpoints are controlled via P-f and Q-V droop laws:

$$f = f_0 - K_p(P - P_{ref}) \quad (4)$$

$$V = V_0 - K_q(Q - Q_{ref}) \quad (5)$$

where K_p and K_q are droop coefficients.

To ensure stable operation with adaptive inertia, the droop coefficient can be a dynamic coefficient linked to inertial response as:

$$K_p = \frac{D(t)}{2H(t)f_0} \quad (6)$$

which ensure that the adaptive tuning of $H(t)$ and $D(t)$ remains consistent with system frequency response.

III. HIGH-LEVEL INTEROPERABLE ARCHITECTURE

At the higher control level, like CTRL3 or 4, an advanced EMS called InMS (Intelligent node Management System) has been proposed during InterSTORE project [18] for optimal management of different services. As shown in Fig. 3, InMS is a hardware and software control platform that integrates algorithms to enable optimal planning and multi-service operation by end-users, based on various storage technologies and their performance in real grid-scale applications. This energy management tool can be configured for different applications, from off-grid (island) to grid-connected applications with external communications with the SCADA of DSO/TSO. Its Real-Time Control and Communications System host real-time execution algorithms (fast dynamics, hybridization, etc.), including the virtualization enabled by the State of the Function concept (SoF), as the figure of merits of the whole hybrid storage system, which provides the system with the appropriate interfaces for high interoperability and supply. Apart from that, it also includes advanced algorithms for adaptive control and parametrization of the GFM converter's inertia parameters, enhancing system stability during disturbances such as frequency or voltage events. As shown in Fig. 3, it provides the possibility of having local/cloud servers that support the operation and optimization of the system in real time.

Fig 3. Scheme of the InMS hierarchy management system.

The server in such architecture hosts the databases and algorithms with slower dynamics, such as daily planning and updating of Advanced Asset Models, both in behavior and degradation, through self-learning techniques such as Machine Learning. Thanks to the hierarchy with fast communication system, various integrated power and energy services such as black-start, inertial response, fast frequency regulation (FFR), voltage dip and POD services can be provided.

The InMS-uGRID Optimal Management System Tool manages distributed energy resources (DERs) through a hierarchical structure spanning fast converter-level control up

to long-term planning and forecasting. Below is the functional decomposition of the advanced management hierarchy used:

- 1- **Subsystem/component level:** this layer covers the fast response functionalities covering distributed algorithms at (Power Electronics) PE level and components controller. It supports and maintains real-time updates which can be executed within 10 to 50 ms cycle supporting fast services.
- 2- **InMS-SHAD layer:** Responsible for fast real time operation covering hybridization of storage elements, optimal real time operation and parameter adaptation for the component level with virtualization of SOF for different asses. At this level it can compute a dimensionless State-of-Function (SoF) vector per asset/service using measured SoH, SoC, Maximum charge/discharge currents, and fault flags, then aggregates to plant-level SoF for dispatch.
- 3- **InMS-uGRID level:** This is a higher level with longer time scale (≥ 1 s to minutes), responsible mainly for planning asset models. Optimal planning, forecasts, tuning and degradation with cycling analysis and power plant control (PPC) level algorithms are mainly at this level.
- 4- **Operator SCADA Interface:** Provides a supervisory dashboard for human-in-the-loop monitoring and control. Supports coordination with utilities (DSO/TSO) via LPC interoperability functions.

Signal interface of InMS is such that it writes active/reactive set-points P^* , Q^* , droops values, current limit, and adaptive inertial parameters of H and D . It also reads: V , f , ROCOF, P , Q and V_{dc} , SOC/SoH, device alarms. End-to-end command latency (LPC + Modbus server) during events is 50–100ms.

A. LPC based Interoperability

The implementation of interoperability within the EMS architecture is fundamentally supported by the State of the Function (SoF) concept, which enables the virtualization of device functionalities across different storage technologies. By abstracting physical capabilities—such as power limits, ramp rates, or service availability—into standardized functional states, SoF allows the EMS to coordinate different energy storage systems (e.g., ultracapacitors and batteries) in a unified and technology-agnostic manner. This virtualized service layer is key to managing hybridized energy storage systems while maintaining a consistent interface for grid-forming control and ancillary services. To enable communication between the EMS and various devices, especially those using legacy protocols, the system integrates an open-source LPC. The LPC acts as a middleware bridge, translating protocols such as Modbus and MQTT into IEEE 2030.5-compliant messages via the NATS messaging layer [19]. Together, the SoF abstraction and LPC-based interoperability framework ensure seamless, standardized coordination of hybrid storage units, enabling the EMS to execute multi-service control strategies across diverse hardware platforms. The deployment of the LPC with bidirectional functionalities represents a critical step toward ensuring seamless interoperability between the distributed energy resources (DERs) and the central Energy Management System (EMS). This deployment focuses on achieving high

performance in fast-response services, particularly by reducing latency in data communication between energy devices and supervisory layers. The main mapping structure for deployment of such an LPC based interoperable system is shown in Fig. 4. This structure ensures efficient bidirectional interaction between existing grid components and the EMS, while leveraging modern virtualization and containerization technologies to enhance deployment and system management.

In this setup, the LPC is deployed locally using a virtual machine that runs two Docker containers—one for the LPC and another for a NATS message queue server, which enables reliable bidirectional communication between DERS and EMS. As shown in Fig. 4, this architecture allows the LPC to handle real-time data exchange, enabling the EMS to read inverter measurements (e.g., active power) and send control commands (e.g., power targets).

Fig 4. Mapping structure of energy management tool.

The EMS/InMS communicates with the Grid-Forming (GFM) device, which integrates a hybrid storage system (UCAP and batteries), as well as with other grid-emulating components. Therefore, the InMS has been enhanced with LPC integration, enabling seamless communication with different storage technologies. Key new functionalities include the implementation of the State of the Function (SoF) as a unified language to manage diverse assets, support for hybridization of ultracapacitors and batteries, and adaptive real-time parameterization of grid-forming control parameters.

B. State of the Function (SoF) algorithm

The diversity of storage technologies (such as ultracapacitors and batteries) and manufacturers poses challenges in comparing and assessing their performance. This is where the State-of-Functions (SoF) framework serves as an advanced interoperability tool. SoF offers a standardized method for describing and evaluating energy storage systems, irrespective of their technology or manufacturer, by breaking them down into functional components like power conversion, energy storage, and control systems, and establishing a common language to define their capabilities.

The figure of merit called State of Function (SoF) has been conceived for the implementation of virtualization, in order to simplify the optimization process and the interoperability with end-users, external systems, and energy or power management systems (EMS or PMS). The State of Function (SoF) is a dimensionless vector that quantifies the availability of one or more storage devices for service operation or grid

functionalities, such as time shifting, primary frequency regulation, or virtual inertia. Fig. 5 shows a system where the hybridization of different technologies can be found.

Fig. 5. Generic scheme of hybridization of different technologies.

As an example, shown on fig. 5, it can be with three different technologies for hybridization:

- Technology 1: ion-lithium battery with high power density ($j = 1$)
- Technology 2: ion-lithium battery with high energy density ($j = 2$)
- Technology 3: ultracapacitors ($j = 3$)

The services that will provide these technologies are:

- Service 1: time shifting and energy arbitrage ($i = 1$)
- Service 2: renewable resources following ($i = 2$)
- Service 3: primary frequency regulation ($i = 3$)
- Service 4: virtual inertia ($i = 4$)

Fig. 6. Scheme example of three different technologies.

Implementing a State of Function (SoF) monitoring system for a HESS system can involve several steps:

1. Identify the relevant system variables: Determine the key parameters that need to be monitored and analyzed to calculate the SoF. This can include variables such as the energy of each DES component, the state of charge (SoC), the state of health (SoH), temperature, voltage, current, maximum/minimum allowed power, and inject/absorb condition modes for each of the storage components.
2. Develop a monitoring system: Install sensors and data acquisition systems to monitor the relevant system variables in real-time. The sensors can be wired or wireless, depending on the specific application. The data acquisition system can be a dedicated system or a software-based solution that collects data from the sensors and processes it.
3. Develop a SoF calculation algorithm: Develop an algorithm that calculates the SoF based on the monitored

system variables. The algorithm can be simple or complex, depending on the specific application. The algorithm should consider the performance characteristics of each storage component and be able to make decisions on how to allocate and balance the service/load between DERs.

4. Integrate the SoF monitoring system with the hybrid energy storage system: Integrate the monitoring system with the hybrid energy storage system so that the SoF can be used for real-time decisions during actual operation.
5. Test and validate the system: Test the SoF monitoring system in real-world conditions and validate its performance. This can involve testing the system under different operating conditions and comparing the results to expected performance metrics.

To calculate the State of Function, it is necessary to introduce several inputs. Graphically, Fig. 7 shows each input/output.

Fig. 7. Inputs/Outputs SoF function.

The algorithm inputs are obtained from measurements or communications and, for each technology, comprise:

- State of Health (SoH): the maximum level of charge of a battery relative to its initial value when it is first used.

$$SOH = [SOH_1 \quad \dots \quad SOH_j] \quad (7)$$

- State of Charge (SoC): the remaining capacity available in the storage system at a given time.

$$SOC = [SOC_1 \quad \dots \quad SOC_j] \quad (8)$$

- Maximum discharge current (i_{max_dis}): maximum current injected by each technology.

$$max_{dis} = [i_{max,dis,1} \quad \dots \quad i_{max,dis,j}] \quad (9)$$

- Maximum charge current (i_{max_ch}): maximum current absorbed by the storage system.

$$\bullet \quad max_{ch} = [i_{max,ch,1} \quad \dots \quad i_{max,ch,j}] \quad (10)$$

- Instantaneous power (iP): power injected or absorbed by each technology.

$$iP = [iP_1 \quad \dots \quad iP_j] \quad (11)$$

- Faults/Alarms (F): in case any of technology is unavailable due to a fault or maintenance.

$$F = [F_1 \quad \dots \quad F_j] \quad (12)$$

Thus, the output of this algorithm can be obtained considering the following:

- Availability matrix (M): This matrix indicates the weight of each parameter in relation to the functionality.
- Corrected availability matrix (M_c): This matrix considers the weight matrix per functionality and technology.
- State of Function (SoF): Dimensionless vector that quantifies the capacity of each system in relation to functionality.

In summary, the function can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} & [M, M_c, SoF] \\ & = SoF_{function}(SOH, SOC, imax_{dis}, imax_{ch}, F, iP) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

So, for each system with different hybridized storage devices it obtained a SoF vector.

The SoF index is mathematically defined as:

$$SoF_i = \sum M_{c,n} \cdot A_{i,n} \quad (14)$$

where $A_{i,n}$ represents normalized availability factors (SoC, SoH, power limits, etc.) and $M_{c,n}$ is the corrected weight per service type. This makes the tool transparent and reproducible.

For calculation SoF the following vector as the pre-asset measurements will be obtained:

$$x = [SoH, SOC, i_{max}^{dis}, i_{max}^{ch}, i_p, F] \quad (15)$$

Then, the SoF engine builds a functionality-specific availability vector via a weighted map $a = M \phi(x)$, where $\phi(x)$ normalizes inputs to $[0,1]$,

$$A_i = [SoH_i, SoC_i, \dots] \quad (16)$$

and applies corrections (faults/deratings) to obtain $a_c = M_c a$. The State-of-Function for asset n and service m is the normalized scalar:

$$SoC_{n,m} = \Psi(a_{c,n,m}) \in [0,1] \quad (17)$$

and plant-level SoF is the aggregator $SoF_s^{plant} = \mathcal{A}(\{SoF_{n,m}\}_n)$ (e.g., max-pooling for power-constrained services, energy-weighted average for energy services). In our experiments, UCAP yields $SoF \approx 1$ for fast services (VI/FFR), while BESS dominates firming, exactly as seen in experimental results section.

As shown in Fig. 8, in a low hierarchy control layer, each storage technology or asset has its own SoF. Following a hierarchical or distributed approach, the EMS/PMS creates a single SoF of the hybrid storage solution or a microgrid. Different approaches can be used for adapting the SoF to the real system application:

- Hierarchical (vertical) approach: Simplifies processing by decoupling low-level issues from top-level operations, enabling lighter real-time and optimization algorithms with multiple virtualization levels. In non-autonomous setups, EMS/PMS guides end-users on external operations and available service combinations.
- Distributed (horizontal) approach: Uses the SoF as a common information base to coordinate with other control or energy management systems, integrating diverse storage technologies, energy vectors, and loads into unified entities like Virtual Storage Plants.

It should be noted that the EMS will allocate UCAP and Battery contributions for different services according to their SoF indices, for example:

$$P_{UCAP}(t) = \alpha(t) \cdot \Delta P(t) \quad (18)$$

$$P_{BESS}(t) = (1 - \alpha(t)) \cdot \Delta P(t) \quad (19)$$

where $P(t)$ is the net requested power for HESS, with:

$$\alpha(t) = \frac{SoF_{UCAP}(t)}{SoF_{UCAP}(t) + SoF_{BESS}(t)} \quad (20)$$

This ensures fast bursts are absorbed by UCAP (high SoF for power services), while the Battery supplies sustained energy (high SoF for energy services). This action is mixed by hybridization process where the UCAP command signal is passing through a high pass filter, and the remaining power will be covered by battery. In this way, considering the SoF status of each element and hybridization process, UCAP will respond to high peaks while battery will recover the response with higher energy for longer responses.

Fig. 8. SoF dimensionless vector for each system.

C. Adaptive and real time parametrization

To enable resilient and flexible operation in low-inertia power systems, the proposed control architecture integrates an adaptive real-time parameterization mechanism within the EMS. This supervisory function dynamically adjusts key parameters of the grid-forming (GFM) converter—specifically, the virtual inertia constant and virtual damping factor (D) based on real-time grid conditions.

In traditional systems, the inertia and damping values are static, selected through offline tuning or worst-case estimation. However, such static configurations can lead to non-optimal or oscillatory behaviors when operating under variable grid conditions. To overcome this, an adaptive control strategy is implemented in the EMS, enabling cycle-by-cycle tuning of inertia and damping in real time. This strategy ensures that the GFM converter remains responsive and stable during a wide range of events, such as voltage dips, frequency events or start up process. For example, as will be demonstrated in the results section, when a voltage dip occurs, a lower virtual inertia value allows the GFM converter to respond more optimal, accelerating the system's recovery once the fault is cleared. After recovery, the inertia can be gradually restored to its nominal higher value, improving stability during steady-state operation. Similarly, during system start-up or frequency instability, adaptive reduction of inertia enables faster synchronization with the grid, while increased damping prevents overshoots and oscillations.

This adaptive behavior is achieved through a self-tuning virtual synchronous generator algorithm, which modulates H and D based on the measured rate of change in key system variables such as frequency or voltage. It should be noted that the implemented approach goes beyond existing adaptive VSM laws by: (1) embedding the adaptive loop within a multi-service EMS, (2) coordinating hybrid storage resources

through SoF with real time hybridization, and (3) ensuring interoperability via standardized LPC-based communication. The active-power loop follows the electromechanical analogy

$$2H\dot{\omega} = P_m - P_e - D(\omega - \omega_0), \quad \dot{\delta} = \omega \quad (21)$$

with power–angle relation linearized around small δ : $P_e \approx \frac{EV}{X}$. In per-unit with base ω_0 , the closed-loop small-signal form used for tuning is:

$$\ddot{\delta} + \frac{D}{2H}\dot{\delta} + \frac{K_s}{2H}\delta = \frac{1}{2H}(P_m - P_{e0}), \quad K_s \approx \frac{EV}{X} \quad (22)$$

The adaptive law modifies the virtual inertia constant H and damping factor D based on measurable system disturbances. For a deviation in frequency Δf or voltage Δv , the following tuning rule is applied:

$$H(t) = H_0 - k_H \frac{d(\Delta f)}{dt} dt \quad (23)$$

$$D(t) = D_0 + k_D |\Delta f| \quad (24)$$

where k_H and k_D are adaptive gains determined by tuning process during event.

During Voltage Regulation (VR) or FFR activation, InMS applies an event-aware update:

$$(H, D) \leftarrow \begin{cases} (H_{min}, D_{max}) & \text{if } |\Delta V| \geq B \\ (H_0, D_0) & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

with smooth ramp back to (H_0, D_0) after clearance of fault: $H(t) = \text{ramp}(H_{min} \rightarrow H_0, T_r)$, $D(t) = \text{ramp}(D_{max} \rightarrow D_0, T_r)$ after fault clearance. Parameters used in VR tests: $B = 0.3$ p.u., $H_0 = 5$ s, $D_0 = 60$, $H_{min} = 0.5$ s, $D_{max} = 100$, current limit of 0.95 p.u., VR droop of 20.

The tuning process of the adaptive inertia and damping control can be formally interpreted using the characteristic polynomial derived from the linearized swing equation:

$$s^2 + \frac{D}{2H}s + \frac{K_s}{2Hv} = 0 \quad (26)$$

This expression is obtained from $\det(sI - A) = 0$, where A is the state matrix of such a two-state swing equation. By adapting $H(t)$ and $D(t)$ dynamically, the eigenvalues and consequently the stability of the system can be determined. Following a tuning process, the EMS maintains $\zeta > 0.2$ for all tested events, ensuring sufficient damping margin without oversizing battery storage following these steps:

- Base selection (H_0, D_0) : choose $\omega_n = \sqrt{\frac{K_s}{2H}}$ considering $t_s \approx \frac{4}{\zeta\omega_n}$ and $\zeta = \frac{D}{2\sqrt{2HK_s}} \in [0.7, 1]$ for well-damped step response in eq (26), using K_s coefficient from the grid equivalent data (Table I)
- Event set (H_{min}, D_{max}) : enforce t_s target (e.g., normally 3 times faster than with H_0) by reducing H until current limit or voltage overshoot are reached; increase D to keep $\zeta \geq 0.7$. This will guarantee the stability margin as well by providing damping without oversizing the battery.
- Threshold (B) : set B from VR activation boundary (3 pu).
- Smooth ramp T_r : select T_r so that $\frac{dH}{dt}$ respects DC-side power availability from UCAP+BESS (SoF-gated). These steps (and values) are those used in Table III and

reproduced in our EMT and lab results.

The proposed solution in real practice is a SoF-based adaptive tuning, wherein the practical ranges of virtual inertia H and damping D are co-scheduled using online flexibility indices of the hybrid storage system. A UCAP dominant weight $a(t)$, which reflects the availability of UCAP from (20) drives a SoF-based inertia schedule:

$$H_{SoF} = H_{min} + a(H_{max} - H_{min}) \quad (27)$$

To preserve the transient quality as H varies, damping is also co-adapted with

$$\zeta^* = \zeta_{min} + a(\zeta_{max} - \zeta_{min}) \quad (28)$$

$$D_{SoF}(t) = 2\zeta^*(t)\sqrt{2H_{SoF}(t)K_s} \quad (29)$$

where H_{SoF} and D_{SoF} will be considered as a supervisory limit of those parameters during HESS operation. Therefore, for designing the controller, in addition to the grid codes limit, physical and operation limits of the devices will be considered. This algorithm dynamically adapt the inertial constants in response to sharp deviations or rapid transients, allowing the system to deliver a fast and controlled response. Once the deviation settles, the parameters return to their nominal values, preserving system robustness. In the EMS implementation, this adaptive logic is embedded within the higher-level control, allowing service-level reconfiguration of storage resources depending on available energy, current system operating mode, and required grid support functions.

The effectiveness of this approach is validated through simulation studies, showing substantial improvements in transient recovery times, and voltage stabilization. This adaptive parameterization not only enhances dynamic stability but also reduces stress on the hybrid energy storage system by better balancing the responses between UCAP and batteries.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

V.A. Simulation-Based Validation (PSCAD EMT)

Before conducting the prototype experimental tests of the developed control architecture in a laboratory environment, a series of detailed PSCAD simulations was carried out. To demonstrate the effectiveness of the GFM control and hybrid solution (HESS) with interoperable adaptive functionality, a weak grid test bench shown in Fig. 9 is considered. The test benchmark presents a full HESS system with a Wind Park which can work on an island thanks to GFM capabilities.

The designed HESS conversion system consists of a battery with a peak power of 8 MW, an energy capacity of 3.494 MWh, and a nominal voltage of 1.15 kV. Additionally, it includes a UCAP rated at 18 MW peak power, with a total capacitance of 170.4 F and a voltage range of 0.97 kV to 1.44 kV. In this HESS system two EMS referred as InMS are utilized. The first, known as InMS-SHAD, is responsible for controlling and parameterizing the GFM conversion unit, ensuring rapid response services by leveraging fast signal acquisition from the DC bus. The second one, InMS-uGRID, operates at a higher level, managing supervision, and interfacing with other electrical assets. The rating and generic technical data of the test systems can be found in Table 1.

Fig. 9. PSCAD test system: HESS connected to an equivalent grid.

TABLE I. SYSTEM DATA FOR PSCAD EMT SIMULATION.

External grid equivalent	Ex. Loads	Local Load	Cable (Lg)
Rating: 100MVA, Inertia: 3.5 s	P= 30 MW Q= 6MVAR	P=1.62 MW Q=0 MVAR	Length: 0,5 km R = 0,125 Ω /km, $X_l = 0,106 \Omega$ /km C = 0,306 μ F/km

V.A.1. Inertial parameters test

In this part of results, the impact of inertia H and damping D on the grid-forming converter was evaluated under a 4 MW load step at $t=6$ s. Figure 10 shows the frequency response for different cases (a fixed D with varying H , and a fixed $H=1$ s with varying D). The results indicate that higher inertia reduces RoCoF and improves nadir but also increases the response time. Conversely, damping strongly influences stability: values below 10 leads to unstable behavior, while higher D improves settling without affecting RoCoF or nadir timing. The summarized indicators (RoCoF and nadir) in Table II further highlight the necessity of adaptive, real-time tuning of both parameters rather than adjusting inertia alone.

Fig. 10. Frequency response: a) for $D=100$ and different H , b) for $H=1$ s and different D .

These observations confirm that inertia and damping must be tuned adaptively to achieve stable and effective inertial response. Appropriate coordination of H and D allows the converter to present a proper inertial response.

TABLE II. SUMMARY OF SYSTEM INDICATORS WITH DIFFERENT INERTIA VALUE

Inertia (H)	RoCoF	Nadir	t Nadir
0.1 sec	0.4 Hz/s	49.920 Hz	6.20 sec
3 sec	0.21 Hz/s	49.935 Hz	6.30 sec
6 sec	0.15 Hz/s	49.943 Hz	6.36 sec
9 sec	0.12 Hz/s	49.950 Hz	6.41 sec
15 sec	0.07 Hz/s	49.960 Hz	6.54 sec

V.A.2. Adaptive control test

In this test, a voltage dip around 10% drop in the voltage has been considered. The comparisons of the voltage at the POI with different controls are shown in Fig. 11.

The improvements on voltage signal happen thanks to the capability of HESS system on proper injection of the required reactive power.

The next graphs on Figs. 12 and 13, show active and reactive power signals. In this test, during Voltage Control (VR) activation, an adaptive inertial approach is also used for selection of inertia value of the converter. As can be observed since the drop of voltage is not high, then the LVRT is not activated and both active and reactive components are contributing to functionalities of the system. Active power changes reflect the converter's inertial response in a weak grid with frequency oscillations during the event.

Fig. 11. 10% voltage dip comparison: No control and VR with adaptive inertial control.

As shown in Table III, when the VR controller is activated a threshold signal (B), Eq (25), is used for activating adaptive inertial tuning of converter at the InMS level.

In such scenario before and long after the dip, normal parametrization with high inertia ($H=5$ s or more) will be used. But during voltage event and recovery after clearing time, a lower inertia constant will be used leading to a faster recovery.

TABLE III. CONTROL PARAMETERS FOR ADAPTIVE VR TEST.

Control Parameters	Value
B (threshold)	0.3
$H1, D1$	5 s, 60
$H2, D2$	0.5 s, 100
VR droop (external controller)	20
Current limit [pu]	0.95

The presented analysis, as well as the analytics provided in Table IV, compares the impact of adaptive inertial parameters during voltage regulation at the POI. Results show that the adaptive approach effectively combines the benefits of high inertia, such as enhanced system stability, while reducing the adverse effects of high recovery time (reduced from 2.1 s to less than 50 ms of HESS response) and inertial impact during voltage disturbances.

TABLE IV. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS-VOLTAGE DIP

Event	V.A.2. Voltage dip	
	No Control	With Control
Settling time	80 ms	10 ms
HESS response	≈ 2.1 s	≤ 50 ms

Fig. 12. Active power POI comparisons: Fixed high and low H, Adaptive approach.

Fig. 13. Reactive power POI comparisons: Fixed high and low H, Adaptive approach.

V.A.3. Frequency event with hybridization test

In this part of analysis, an under-frequency event is created to test the frequency response of the full management tool with proper hybridization between two different storage devices (UCAP and Battery). From the event caused by a load step change, it can be observed that the frequency drop is strong and will reach almost 46 Hz. Compared responses of the system frequency with and without activation of fast frequency control at the PPC level are shown in Fig. 14.

For this test the droop (statism) of the controller has been designed to 1% and with that, the controller was able to improve the drop of frequency significantly. Comparing Fig. 14 with Fig. 15, it can be observed that, in this case, the dynamic response improvement is due to the high power injected by the HESS system.

Fig. 14. Frequency variation at POI with low-inertia grid.

Fig. 15. Active power at POI with low-inertia grid.

Fig. 16 presents that UCAP assumes the fast response, while the battery has a more relaxed shape. From Fig. 17 it can be observed that the SOC of the UCAP changes quickly but not for the battery. The UCAP, with its larger capacity, provided a faster response, while the battery offered a slower response reaching its limited capacity. Further analytical insights can be found in Table V, where the values of RoCoF and Nadir show significant improvements, reaching 0.6 Hz/s and 49.15 Hz after controller activation, respectively.

Fig. 16. UCAP and BESS power.

Fig. 17. UCAP and BESS state of charge.

TABLE V. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS- FREQUENCY EVENT.

Event	V.A.I. Frequency	
	No Control	With Control
RoCoF [Hz/s]	0.88	0.60
Nadir [Hz]	46.10	49.15
HES response	----	≤ 80 ms

V.B. Experimental Validation (Lab Setup)

The implementation was carried out in the Megawatt-scale Spanish GridLab, which provides a modular and scalable platform for validating advanced control and interoperability functions under realistic grid conditions. As shown in Fig. 18, various Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) interface with the proposed InMS energy management system, exchanging real-time data via the LPC and standardized communication protocols. The setup consists of two main parts. The Test Bench (on the left) includes four configurable converter stations that replicate weak/strong grids, renewable profiles, and fault events, enabling controlled testing scenarios. The second part (on the right) is the HESS under Test (HUT), which integrates UCAP-BESS hybridization and the novel control strategies developed in this work.

The InMS is deployed on industrial-grade ICT hardware with dual servers for real-time and cloud-based functions. Measurements are sampled at 2.5 kHz, while supervisory commands are exchanged using Modbus-TCP and LPC/NATS middleware. This architecture enables the evaluation of weak-grid operation, black-start sequences, and fast service provision under realistic industrial conditions. Main components of the test bench:

- 2x commercial energy management tool based on InMS technology's ICT systems – with measurement, management, operation, and control capacity over the bench's equipment.
- 4x 277 kVA - Bidirectional power converters, model FS4G located in GridLab.
- DC connection and decoupling cabinet.

- Isolation transformer 400/400 VAC – 250 kVA

Apart from that, the HUT part integrates advanced control algorithms and hybrid storage technologies developed within the case study to validate grid-forming functionalities and real-time service provision. The following is a summary of the elements in this part of the lab:

Advanced InMS tool consists of the developed controls, with the ability of fast response to events.

- AC/DC power converter – 250 kVA
- DC/DC power converter 250 kVA
- Isolation transformer 470/400 V_{AC} – 250 kVA
- Battery Rack – 200 kWh / 1000 V_{DC}
- UCAP racks and control system, with a capacity of 20-45 s / 250 kW.

Following this section, it presents the details of the technical results of selected real-life validation tests conducted in the advanced GridLab facility located in Valencia, Spain.

These demonstrations were carried out to assess the performance, interoperability, and robustness of the deployed control and communication solutions under realistic operating conditions. The test setup includes two DERs: DER1 with the HESS under test equipped with a GFM converter and EMS/LPC interface, and DER2 which has an advanced test bench capable of emulating various grid conditions through programmable power converters. These tests focused on validating startup capabilities, system response to disturbances, and real-time multi-service provision using the adaptive and interoperable EMS framework.

Three key scenarios were evaluated. The first involved the black start and energization of DER1 operating in GFM mode, coordinating with DER2 in GFL mode to establish a stable islanded microgrid. The second test simulated a 100% voltage dip, triggering the EMS to activate the automatic transfer system (ATS) for shift from grid connected mode to island mode, isolating the microgrid, and later reconnect once normal conditions were restored. The final test assessed the system's

Fig. 18. Experimental setup: Diagram of main elements in GridLab.

ability to deliver fast grid services, including virtual inertia and fast frequency response (FFR), leveraging the State of the Function (SoF) mechanism and real-time parameter adaptation. These scenarios collectively demonstrate the robustness, flexibility, and service-oriented capabilities of the HESS platform under realistic conditions. The following Table VI summarizes the main test parameters and conditions applied during the demonstrations.

TABLE VI. CONTROL MODE AND GENERIC PARAMETERS OF CONVERTER

Parameters	Value
Grid Nom. Voltage	400 V
Frequency	50 Hz
VSC rated current	390 A
VSC rated kVA	250 kVA
Transformer1	400/470 (250 kVA)
Transformer2 Grid/VSC	400/400 (250 kVA)
Nominal DC voltage	600 Vdc
Frequency droop default value	2%
Voltage droop	5%
Voltage rise time	100 ms
Emulated inertia (H) default	1 s

V.B.1. Test 1 - Black start and synchronization

As explained, the first experimental test is focused on assessing the capability of the grid-forming operation of DER1 in island mode according to the developed architecture. The results obtained are presented in Figs. 19 to 21.

As shown in Fig. 19, the grid forming converter was able to start smoothly with a ramp control. This figure shows the voltages at the point of connection. At this test, the impact of high peaks during start-up is reduced, and the transient is soft and acceptable. Based on the results shown on Figs. 20 and 21, the converter initially passes the black start in island mode, independently generating voltage and frequency references. Around the timestamp of 0.6 min, the EMS controller activates the synchronizer, which aligns the voltage phase and frequency of DER1 with the main grid. The figure shows the synchronization process, after which the synchronization error drops to zero.

After synchronization, the main breaker gets closed to connect the islanded system to the main grid. Subsequently, after that, the converter transitions to grid-connected mode, showing small dynamic variations in active and reactive current due to interactions with the grid, confirming proper and acceptable functionality during the operational mode change.

Fig. 19. Start-up of the HESS converter in island mode, with Ramp control.

Fig. 20. Full synchronization test: synchronizer OFF on island, Synchronizer is ON, switched to the grid-connected mode.

Fig. 21. AC and DC power signals: synchronizer OFF in island, Synchronizer is ON, switched to the grid-connected mode.

V.B.2. Test 2 - Voltage dip and ATS operation

This test involves voltage drops with a 100 % dip for a long duration (around 2 min). In some real-life cases, when an external voltage dip lasts too long, industrial consumers decide to disconnect from the faulty grid while continuing to supply their critical loads locally. In such scenarios, having an interoperable GFM solution capable of operating on island and maintaining power to critical loads is highly beneficial. The goal of this test is to demonstrate the capability of the HESS energy management tool to provide grid quality and stability services to industrial customers during voltage dips. Within the same test setup as before, the event is created by means of the power converters PCS3 and PCS4 on the test bench side. PCS4 creates the grid, and PCS3 oversees creating different voltage dips in the system. The results of this demonstration are shown in Figs. 22-25. As shown on Fig. 22, the long-term voltage dip happened at 0.5 min of the experiment. Thanks to the EMS control action with the ATS (Automatic Transfer Switch) algorithm, the fault has been detected, and the converter of DER1 gets disconnected from the grid. After clearing the fault around 2.5 min of the experiment (of a 2-minute fault), the synchronizer is ON. The blue curve shows the error of the synchronizer, which after a while the error is zero and the converter switched to grid-connected mode with a fast transient for voltage recovery. The designed ATS is configured in a way that, with some given variation, in this test configured for $\pm 5\%$ of variations, on the nominal voltage at the point of measurement (in this test at the PoC), it starts to react by opening the main breaker, moving the system in island mode while at the same time the voltage of island (green curve, Fig. 22) is kept for feeding the local loads. As soon as the fault is detected, ATS will send a command signal

opening the breaker, which usually takes 50 ms to 100 ms over Ethernet to a Modbus server. Fig. 23 shows the AC power signals as well proofing stable operation of GFM feeding the local load during island.

Fig. 22. Full voltage dip test, for a long period of time, 1100 ms. Showing three steps: a) island operation, b) synchronization after clearing the fault, and c) grid connection.

Fig. 23. Power signals, AC and DC, during full voltage dip tests.

The smooth, transient, and stable performance of the system is thanks to the contribution from the UCAP and Battery on the DC side. To show the contribution on the DC side, additional analysis has been done to monitor and extract the raw data from the DC side shown on Fig. 24. The combined current contribution of the battery and UCAP under different situations, from startup to voltage dip test, is presented on Fig. 24. The UCAP supplies high bursts of current during fast transients, whereas the battery delivers steadier current for better recovery and supports UCAP maintaining its SOC, proving the complementary nature of hybrid storage. In addition to that, the monitored values of SoF signals for different storage elements are also presented on Fig. 25.

Fig. 24. Storage current during the startup and voltage dip tests.

The State of Function (SoF) values for both UCAP and battery for different power/energy services are displayed, highlighting UCAP’s high SoF (close to 1) for fast services (power) and the battery’s higher SoF for Energy service. This

validates the interoperability toolkit’s ability to prioritize resources based on service requirements.

Fig. 25. SoF values during events: Voltage dip, and start-up tests.

V.B.3. Test 3 - Multi-service operation with renewable profile

The objective of this last test is to evaluate the performance of the GFL and GFM converters within the implemented interoperable tool with SoF operation for testing multiple services (firming and frequency event). As illustrated in Figs. 26 and 27, two of the grid-following converter stations, namely PCS3 and PCS4, are configured to emulate a weak grid and a renewable energy source, respectively. In this scenario, PCS4 is designed to replicate the behavior of a low-inertia weak grid, while PCS3 is controlled to operate as a variable renewable source, such as a photovoltaic system.

To assess the functionality of the HESS system, two continuous events are implemented: a virtual inertia test and a power firming test. In the first one, PCS4 operates as a weak grid. An under-frequency event (shown in Fig. 26) is intentionally introduced to evaluate the response of the developed HESS system.

The goal is to analyze the system’s capability to support frequency stability through inertia emulation.

Fig. 26. Power profile generated by PSC4.

Fig. 27. Power profile generated by PSC3 for firming test.

Following the virtual inertia test, a firming service is conducted using PCS3. In this test, as shown in Fig. 27, a realistic PV generation profile is applied to PCS3 to emulate typical fluctuations in solar power output. Simultaneously, the response of the Hybrid Energy Storage System (HESS), equipped with an advanced grid-forming (GFM) DER1 controller integrating ultracapacitors (UCAP) and batteries, was analyzed and demonstrated.

The results of this test are presented on figs. 28 to 31. The obtained results highlight the successful interoperability of the SoF algorithm and the effective hybridization of different energy storage technologies, where InMS dynamically coordinates DERs based on real-time storage status. The capture of GFM converter equipped with HESS are presented in Figs. 28 and 29. Fig. 28 illustrates the active power injection as well as important signals from the HESS DER1 during a virtual inertia (VI) event, where the ultracapacitor (UCAP) rapidly responds to frequency deviations.

Fig. 28. Power Real-time interface of the HESS DER1 system response during VI event.

The fast power delivery demonstrates UCAP's dominance in high-speed services, while the State of Function (SoF) remains high (close to 1), confirming its suitability for fast grid support. In Fig. 29, the capture is related to a firming event after the VI test. In this part of the test battery plays a crucial role in power firming, providing sustained energy output compared to UCAP. The hybridization strategy ensures optimal resource allocation, with the battery's SoF being higher for firming services, while UCAP contributes less.

Fig. 29. Real time exchange of the HESS DER1 system response during firming event.

Additional analysis of the measured DC-side signals, shown in Fig. 30, highlights the complementary behavior of the hybrid storage system. The ultracapacitor delivers high current bursts during virtual inertia events, while the battery provides steady current during firming, confirming effective coordination

between the two elements. The successful implementation of SoF is also further analyzed within the plots of Fig. 31. The SoF values are highlighting UCAP's high SoF (close to 1) for fast services (VI) and the battery's higher SoF for firming.

This confirms the system's capability to allocate resources dynamically based on service needs through the interoperability framework.

Fig. 30. Current contribution of HESS system in DER1 - Hybridization of BESS and UCAP.

Fig. 31. SoF values during test events, VI and Firming with LPC.

The main insights gained from the experiments are summarized as follows:

- The experimental validation provided several important insights. Both PSCAD simulations and laboratory results consistently confirmed the benefits of hybridization combined with adaptive inertia and damping. The UCAP delivered a sub-100 ms response that significantly improved the frequency nadir, while the BESS ensured sustained energy delivery. This division of roles also reduced stress on the battery and is expected to mitigate long-term aging by alleviating rapid power swings at the DC link.
- The incorporation of adaptive inertia tuning proved critical for future deployment of grid-forming converters in low-inertia systems. In the laboratory tests, adaptive tuning improved recovery time by more than 75% compared to fixed-inertia control. At the same time, the validation highlighted that different events require opposite strategies: frequency disturbances benefit from higher inertia to limit ROCOF and support nadir, whereas voltage dips are better managed with lower inertia and stronger damping to maintain converter agility for reactive voltage support. A simple event-classification rule (P-channel vs. Q-channel) was sufficient to enable this switching in

practice.

- The concept of State of Function (SoF) provided a unique and unified metric for monitoring and orchestrating storage assets. SoF-based allocation successfully mapped services to the most suitable device: UCAP consistently scored higher for fast, short-duration services, while the BESS was assigned energy-dominant tasks. This ensured that adaptive actions remained feasible with respect to device headroom, avoiding overstressing storage when limited while still allowing aggressive inertia when available.

Finally, the interoperability layer based on low-power communications (LPC) was effective in practice, allowing seamless transitions between grid-connected and islanded operation. Collectively, these findings demonstrate the technical soundness and practical feasibility of the proposed adaptive and interoperable management framework, validated in both EMT simulation and HIL laboratory setups.

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed control architecture enables coordinated operation of ultracapacitors and batteries to deliver key grid services such as virtual inertia, frequency regulation, and voltage dip mitigation. A core innovation is the hierarchical management framework with SoF, which virtualizes and monitors the real-time status of storage assets to enable intelligent, technology-agnostic coordination. This includes SoF-based adaptive tuning of the GFM converter's inertia and damping, improving dynamic performance during severe disturbances by reducing inertia for faster recovery. The framework—spanning device, coordination, and EMS levels—has been validated in PSCAD and megawatt-scale laboratory tests, demonstrating its practical viability. Together with the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) for interoperability, the system offers a scalable and robust solution for hybrid storage management in future low-inertia grids.

Quantitative results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed approach. In PSCAD simulations, the frequency Nadir and RoCoF improved by 78% and 31%, respectively, compared to the uncontrolled case during frequency event. The recovery time after clearing a voltage dip fault was reduced to less than 50 ms for the HESS response and 10 ms for the monitored voltage signal, demonstrating the advantage of the SoF-based adaptive strategy over fixed-inertia control. These improvements are particularly relevant for system operators, who benefit from a combination of meaningful inertia support and rapid post-fault recovery.

Experimental validation in GridLab further demonstrated the capability of grid-forming converters to sustain island operation against long-term voltage disturbances. With ATC operation, voltage recovery times were consistently below 100 ms after fault clearance. Moreover, the HESS operated reliably under the supervision of the SoF-based management system, confirming the practical performance gains of the proposed adaptive, interoperable control framework. Thanks to the fast frequency support provided by UCAP, battery stress was significantly reduced, which can extend battery lifetime and enhance overall system durability.

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